

Editorial

Faith, Commitment and Action

Now that we have a new president in the United States, it is useful to go back to six years ago, soon after the release of the ecological encyclical *Laudato Si'* (Francis, 2015).

The then Vice President Biden issued a sweeping endorsement of Pope Francis soon after publication of the Vatican's draft encyclical on climate change, saying of the pontiff, "We have a good one now" (Warrick, 2015).

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The remarks came during a speech that was Biden's first public appearance since the funeral services for his son, Beau Biden, who died of brain cancer, on 30 May 2015.

"There's a consensus growing," Biden said, after quoting from media coverage of the leaked encyclical, the official version of

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which is due to be issued Thursday. “This doesn’t only have a moral component to it. It has a security component to it, as well as an economic component.”

The Vatican then accepted the scientific consensus linking human activity to global warming and calls on the world’s wealthy nations to reduce consumption and cut back on the use of fossil fuels. The draft document chastises climate-change deniers and says the “poor and the Earth are shouting” for action on addressing the causes of warming.

Biden, addressing a White House-sponsored forum on clean-energy investment, noted the recent activism on climate change by a wide range of religious communities, “from leading evangelicals ... to the pope.”

“I’m a practising Catholic. I always joke – they say, ‘Why am I a practising Catholic?’ I say, ‘Because of the nuns and Jesuits,’” Biden said. Then he added, referring to the church’s first Jesuit pope: “We have a good one now.”

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Biden went on to read excerpts from an article about the leaked draft from The Washington Post, which in a verbal slip, he referred to as “The Washington Pope.”

“Post. Pope, heh,” he said, correcting the error. “They sometimes think they’re ‘pope.’”

Echoing several of the draft encyclical’s themes, Biden warned that the world was rapidly approaching a “point of no return” for preventing severe impacts from climate change, and he berated members of Congress and climate-change skeptics for blocking progress on reducing greenhouse gases.

“It’s not only the morally right thing to do, it’s also a smart economic play,” said Biden, describing climate change as the “single-most important” challenge facing the administration.

Let us hope that President Biden’s Catholic faith will continue to shape his political, economic and social concerns and commitments, in line with the present Pope’s (Groppe, 2021)

Further, we are happy to inform that AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies has gone fully online. It will be available a www.punejournal.co.in. We have also been ISSN for the E-Journal (E-2582-791X). We hope that our readers will be able to make better use of our journal with its Electronic version.

Editor

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